

**QUEEN'S
UNIVERSITY
BELFAST**

Experimental verification of broadband mmWave RIS-aided communications: codebook-based beam steering and indoor channel measurements

Kasem, F., MacHado, G., Cotton, S., Abbasi, M. A. B., & Zelenchuk, D. (2025). Experimental verification of broadband mmWave RIS-aided communications: codebook-based beam steering and indoor channel measurements. In *19th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP 2025): Proceedings* (EuCAP Proceedings). Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers Inc..
<https://doi.org/10.23919/EuCAP63536.2025.10999970>

Published in:

19th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP 2025): Proceedings

Document Version:

Peer reviewed version

Queen's University Belfast - Research Portal:

[Link to publication record in Queen's University Belfast Research Portal](#)

Publisher rights

Copyright 2025 The Authors.

This manuscript is distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution License (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the author and source are cited.

General rights

Copyright for the publications made accessible via the Queen's University Belfast Research Portal is retained by the author(s) and / or other copyright owners and it is a condition of accessing these publications that users recognise and abide by the legal requirements associated with these rights.

Take down policy

The Research Portal is Queen's institutional repository that provides access to Queen's research output. Every effort has been made to ensure that content in the Research Portal does not infringe any person's rights, or applicable UK laws. If you discover content in the Research Portal that you believe breaches copyright or violates any law, please contact openaccess@qub.ac.uk.

Open Access

This research has been made openly available by Queen's academics and its Open Research team. We would love to hear how access to this research benefits you. – Share your feedback with us: <http://go.qub.ac.uk/oa-feedback>

Experimental verification of broadband mmWave RIS-aided communications: codebook-based beam steering and indoor channel measurements

Ferhad Kasem*, Gabriel Machado†, Simon Cotton*, Muhammad Ali Babar Abbasi *and Dmitry Zelenchuk *

*Centre for Wireless Innovation (CWI), School of Electronics, Electrical Engineering and Computer Science (EEECS), Queen’s University Belfast, Belfast, U.K.

†School of Engineering, Ulster University, Belfast, UK

f.kasem@qub.ac.uk, m.abbasi@qub.ac.uk and d.zelenchuk@qub.ac.uk

Abstract—This paper summarises the design and channel measurements of a wideband Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface RIS operating within the millimeter wave spectrum for 5G and beyond communication. RIS elements are controlled by a p-i-n diode and biased via RF chokes operating within the n257 millimeter wave 5G band. The RIS operates in both vertical and horizontal polarization. Experiments have been performed to validate the performance of the RIS in both near-field and far-field regions. It has been experimentally demonstrated that the proposed RIS can reflect incident beams towards desired locations with channel gain enhancement of up to 16.3 dB when appropriate phase profiles are applied.

Index Terms—5G, 6G, RIS, phase shift, p-i-n diodes, varactors, channel measurements, power spectrum, unit cell, beam steering

I. INTRODUCTION

The 5th generation of wireless communication networks (5G) has been widely deployed globally, offering enhanced mobile broadband services, ultra-reliable low-latency communications, and massive machine-type communications [1]. One of the key enabling technologies for 5G is utilizing millimeter-wave (mmWave) frequency bands, making it possible to achieve the highest recorded data rates and increase network capacity due to the abundance of bandwidth. However, the radio channel propagation characteristics at mmWave frequencies have always been challenging due to the higher free-space path loss, larger sensitivity to blockages, poor penetration through objects, and higher atmospheric attenuation (e.g., rain and Oxygen fading) [2]. To address such challenges and to provide ultra-high data rates and ultra-low latency communication, extensive efforts have been put into innovative and cutting-edge technologies to not only support mmWave 5G but also to develop the 6th generation of wireless communication networks. It is now well established that Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) is amongst the physical layer technologies that have been proposed and developed to be a part of 6G, in addition to ultra massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO), THz technologies [3]. RIS-aided communications have been proposed as an essential key enabling technology of 6G to overcome coverage problems and link instability at mmWave frequencies [4]. RIS technology provides extended

coverage by creating artificial line-of-sight (LOS) links in case of blind spots caused by blockages in the direct LOS between transmitters and receivers [5]. RISs are surfaces formed by planar arrays of sub-wavelength reflecting unit cells. These unit cells are designed and optimized to control the amplitude and the phase of the incoming EM waves. Active components such as p-i-n diodes and varactors are often embedded in the aperture of unit cells to control the amplitude and phase of the incoming waves. Such inexpensive components have low energy consumption, allowing for massive deployment of RIS technology [6]. The network performance enhancement promised by ideal RISs has been theoretically confirmed in the literature at a system level [7]. However, to demonstrate the feasibility of RIS technology, efforts into the practical implementation of RIS have been accelerated recently. For example, practical RIS designs operating at mmWave frequencies have been reported in [8], [9] where near-field and far-field measurements were reported. Another RIS testbed operating at sub-6 GHz frequencies was developed in [10] and real-time transmission scenarios of RIS were investigated to record received power levels for different receiver locations in an indoor environment. Against this background, there is still somewhat of a scarcity in the literature on the practical implementation of RIS and channel measurements, especially at mmWave frequencies.

Contributions – This paper aims to present an experimental verification of a RIS developed to operate at the n257 frequency band (26.5 – 29.5 GHz). This verification is achieved through near-field and far-field beam steering at different receiver locations by incorporating a codebook design into RIS without random optimization to find optimal RIS configurations. The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the RIS prototype and the codebook design of RIS profiles. Section III presents the experimental setup and the obtained results of the proposed RIS prototype. Section IV concludes the paper.

II. RIS DESIGN AND SIMULATION

The layout of the RIS array used in measurements is depicted in Fig. 1. It consists of two interleaved 20-by-20

Fig. 1. Layout of the proposed wideband 1-bit dual-polarization RIS.

unit-cell arrays, making the total number of unit-cells in the RIS 800 elements. Each of these 20-by-20 arrays supports a different polarization. This array configuration, also called the checkerboard configuration, enables dual linear-polarization operation. For conciseness, the experimental characterization of only the full RIS design will be presented in this paper. The constituting unit cell of this RIS has been extensively examined in [11], [12], regarding its design topology, phase control technology, reflective characteristics, and bandwidth.

The total array size is $92.6 \times 92.6 \text{ mm}^2$, equivalent to $8.4\lambda \times 8.4\lambda$, where λ is the free-space wavelength at 27 GHz. The proposed RIS comprises three stacked substrates with different thicknesses and material types, while the phase shift registers that control the unit cells lay on the bottom layer. The middle layer connects between the unit cells and shift registers. The proposed RIS is configured based on phase distribution profiles, which if applied to RIS elements, will generate the desired shape and direction of the reflected beams. For a RIS designed in the xy -plane, the phase distribution required for RIS elements to steer the incident beam towards a desired location is calculated based on the reflect array theory through the following equation:

$$\phi_{i,j} = k_0 (R_{i,j} - \sin \theta_0 (x_i \cos \varphi_0 + y_j \sin \varphi_0)) + \phi_0, \quad (1)$$

where i, j are the indexes of the elements along the x - and y - axes, respectively, k_0 is the wave number at the center frequency, $R_{i,j}$ is the distance from the transmitter (Tx) to the $(i, j)^{th}$ unit-cell, (x_i, y_j) represents the position of each unit-cell in the Cartesian coordinate system, (θ_0, φ_0) are the Spherical coordinate system angles, and ϕ_0 is a constant reference phase. This criterion is foundational for the codebook design that contains phase distribution information required for RIS placed at a certain distance from a Tx and programmed to reflect the incident beam to certain locations. Each unit cell incorporates a single p-i-n diode in its structure, allowing the aperture to have two distinct states by switching the p-i-n diode *on* and *off*. Hence, the continuous phase shift in

Fig. 2. Normalized RCS of vertically-polarized beams reflected of RIS at 0° , 15° , 45° , and 60° at 27.5 GHz.

the complex plane can be quantized using a binary phase modulation scheme. For example, for a continuous phase ranging between 0° and 360° , the $0^\circ - 179^\circ$ range can be mapped to 0° and the $180^\circ - 360^\circ$ range can be mapped to 180° . Consequently, each state of the p-i-n diode is mapped to one of these quantized phase values (e.g., the *off* state is mapped to 0° phase and the *on* state is mapped to 180° phase).

$$\varphi_{ij} = \begin{cases} 0^\circ, & \varphi_{ij} < 180^\circ \\ 180^\circ, & \varphi_{ij} \geq 180^\circ \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where φ_{ij} is the quantized phase of the unit cell i, j in the planar array. The proposed RIS has been primarily designed for incident angles of -30° to 0° . The phase distribution of RIS elements is calculated using the criteria explained in equations (1) and (2). The normalized simulated 2D reflected beams represented by the radar cross section (RCS) of the proposed RIS at 27.5 GHz and at the reflection angles 0° , 15° , 45° , and 60° are presented in Fig. 2. It can be observed that a significant gain can be attained when RIS is turned *on* and configured to reflect the beam to a certain angle compared to when RIS is in the *off* state. For example, when RIS operates in the vertical polarization mode and is excited by a wave incoming from -30° on the azimuth plane at 27.5 GHz, peak gains of 22.2 dB, 18.4 dB, 15 dB, and 22.3 dB are achieved when RIS is respectively configured to reflect the beam to 0° , 15° , 45° , and 60° compared to when RIS is *off*.

III. RIS HARDWARE AND MEASUREMENTS

The fabricated prototype of the proposed RIS consists of six stacked layers, where the control circuit is implemented on the back layer of the fabricated RIS tile. The power supply port contains a positive voltage (+3 to 5 V) and a ground input, which can be connected to a DC power source. The fabricated RIS will be shown later in this paper in the experiment setup.

A. Near-field measurements

The RF measurement setup of the proposed RIS in the near field region is demonstrated in Fig. 3. Two standard-gain horn antennas are connected to Keysight (Model used is Agilent) E8361C PNA Network Analyzer and utilized as a Tx

Fig. 3. Measurement setup to evaluate the RIS performance when the transmitter antenna is in the near-field region.

and a receiver (Rx). The measurement setup was constructed and placed inside the anechoic chamber. The Tx is placed at a distance of 40 cm and -30° rotation from the center of RIS in the azimuth plane. The Tx horn antenna and RIS are held and supported by 3D-printed fixtures installed on the turntable. The Rx horn antenna is placed 2 meters from the center of the RIS. The Rx horn antenna remains stationary to measure the reflected beam, while the Tx horn antenna rotates simultaneously with the RIS on the turntable from -90° to 90° with 2° steps. It is worth noting that the 40 cm distance and -30° azimuth rotation between the Tx and RIS is always maintained during the rotation cycle. The RIS reflects the incident beam to desired directions based on specific phase distributions applied to RIS. These phases are produced by changing the biasing conditions of the p-i-n diode in RIS elements. The phase distribution required to reflect the incident beam to certain locations is a function of the operating frequency, the number of RIS elements and the spacing between them, and the location of Tx and Rx. The phase distribution information of each desired reflection angle is stored in the codebook. The measured S_{21} between the Tx and the Rx determines the received power captured by Rx, which relates to the gain of the RIS. The beam steering capability of the proposed RIS is illustrated through the measured 2D patterns of the reflected beams at several reflection angles on the azimuth plane, as shown in Fig. 4.

These figures show the S_{21} parameter when RIS is turned *on* and configured to reflect the incident beam to certain angular directions versus when RIS is *off*. As illustrated in the figures, a significant gain improvement (greater than 15 dB) is observed when RIS is turned *on* compared to when RIS is *off* at all reflection angles. Therefore, it can be deduced that the proposed RIS can reflect incident beams up to 60° along the azimuth plane. It is also crucial to indicate that the presence of lobes other than the desired main lobe at the desired reflection angle results from the 1-bit phase quantization generated by the p-i-n diode in each unit cell, and a relatively small aperture size of RIS. Due to the binary operation of p-i-n diodes, they only generate two states with approximately 180° phase difference, resulting in 1-bit phase quantization. This 1-bit phase discretization degrades the reflection performance of RIS by impacting the gain and the beam steering accuracy.

Fig. 4. Measured beams reflected of RIS at 28 GHz and the corresponding phase distributions for every reflection angle. (a) 0° reflection. (b) 15° reflection. (c) 45° reflection. (d) 60° reflection.

Moreover, in some cases, it generates lobes in the sidelobe region comparable to the desired main lobe. Many techniques in the literature have been utilized to alleviate the quantization lobes including genetic algorithm (GA), reference phase optimization, aperture phase optimization, and selection of feed location [13]. These techniques will be investigated and examined further in our future work.

B. Far-field measurements

Unlike reflect array antenna-based RIS measurements (widely reported in the literature) where the feed is located at a fixed distance from the array, practical RIS devices are expected to be placed in dynamic environments where Tx to RIS and RIS to Rx distances are larger. The incident beams from base stations can be projected to RISs from arbitrary distances; therefore, testing RIS in an environment where far-field conditions are met is essential. In the previous measurement test in the anechoic chamber, the proposed RIS was tested such that the Tx antenna was in the near-field region and the Tx and RIS were rotating while Rx was stationary. To validate the RIS performance in a practical indoor environment in the far-field region, an increased Tx-RIS distance is used to ensure plane wave excitation of RIS. In this indoor experimental setup, shown in Fig. 5, the Tx horn antenna is placed 2.2 m from RIS with normal incidence, while the Rx horn antenna is placed 2.5 m from RIS.

The RIS remains stationary while the Rx location will be rotated off of RIS to 15° , 30° , 45° , and 60° , respectively on the azimuth plane while maintaining the 2.5 meter distance from RIS. Both Tx and Rx are identical 15 dBi standard-gain horn antennas. The Tx horn antenna is connected to a continuous-wave Keysight (Agilent) 83650B signal generator, while the Rx horn antenna is connected to a Rhode & Schwarz FSQ 40 signal analyzer. The input power of the signal generator is

Fig. 5. Indoor RIS measurement setup in the far field.

Fig. 6. Measured received power at 15° reflection in the far-field and their corresponding phase distribution profiles. (a) at 27 GHz. (b) at 27.5 GHz. (c) at 28 GHz. (d) at 28.5 GHz. (e) at 29 GHz. (f) at 29.5 GHz.

set to 10 dBm. The sampled bandwidth is 10 MHz with 600 points. The DC power supply provides the required biasing voltages and currents to the RIS's p-i-n diodes. The received power spectrum when RIS is *off* versus when RIS is *on* and reflects the incident beam to 15° at several frequency points in the far field are shown in Fig. 6. From Fig. 6, it can be deduced that when RIS is *on* and configured to reflect the incident beam to 15° , gain enhancements of 13.2 dB, 15.1 dB, 16.3 dB, 11.9 dB, 14.1 dB, and 12.7 dB are obtained compared to the *off* state of RIS at the specified frequencies. On average, a gain enhancement of 13.9 dB is obtained in the 27–29.5 GHz range. On the other hand, the received power spectrum when

Fig. 7. Measured received power at 45° reflection in the far-field and their corresponding phase distribution profiles. (a) at 27 GHz. (b) at 27.5 GHz. (c) at 28 GHz. (d) at 28.5 GHz. (e) at 29 GHz. (f) at 29.5 GHz.

RIS reflects the incident beam to 45° is shown in Fig. 7. From Fig. 7, it can be observed that when RIS is *on* and configured to reflect the incident beam to 45° , gain enhancements of 15.7 dB, 13.8 dB, 13 dB, 15.2 dB, 15.8 dB, and 13.3 dB are obtained compared to the *off* state of RIS at the same specified frequencies. On average, a gain enhancement of 14.5 dB is obtained in the 27–29.5 GHz range.

Furthermore, the received power spectrum when RIS reflects the incident beam to 60° is shown in Fig. 8. From Fig. 8, it can be observed that when RIS is *on* and configured to reflect the incident beam to 45° , gain enhancements of 17.2 dB, 14.7 dB, 11.5 dB, 15.1 dB, 14.1 dB, and 16.3 dB are obtained compared to the *off* state of RIS at the same specified frequencies. On average, a gain enhancement of 14.8 dB is obtained in the 27–29.5 GHz range. From both near-field and far-field measurements, it is reasonable to conclude that the proposed RIS enhances the gain by at least 15 dB from 0° to 60° across the targeted n257 frequency band.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper summarises the design, hardware, and experimental characterization of a wideband dual-polarized mmWave RIS for B5G/6G applications. The proposed RIS operates effectively within the 27–29.5 GHz range, covering the n257 mmWave 5G band in both the near-field and far-field conditions. The proposed RIS reflects incident beams

Fig. 8. Measured received power at 60° reflection in the far-field and their corresponding phase distribution profiles. (a) at 27 GHz. (b) at 27.5 GHz. (c) at 28 GHz. (d) at 28.5 GHz. (e) at 29 GHz. (f) at 29.5 GHz.

to desired locations by applying specific phase distributions to RIS elements. The phase distribution information for specific frequencies, Tx-RIS distances, and RIS-Rx distances are stored in a codebook. Experimental results showed strong beam steering performance and gain enhancement in both the anechoic chamber and indoor environment.

V. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work is partially supported by the Department for the Economy of Northern Ireland under U.S. Ireland Research and Development Partnership under Grant USI 199, in part by the Horizon Europe Project 6G-SANDBOX funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under Grant 101096328, and in part by the Project REASON sponsored by the Department of Science Innovation and Technology (DSIT).

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Ghosh, A. Maeder, M. Baker, and D. Chandramouli, "5G evolution: A view on 5G cellular technology beyond 3GPP Release 15," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 127 639–127 651, 2019.
- [2] I. A. Hemadeh, K. Satyanarayana, M. El-Hajjar, and L. Hanzo, "Millimeter-wave communications: Physical channel models, design considerations, antenna constructions, and link-budget," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 870–913, 2018.
- [3] C.-X. Wang, X. You, X. Gao, X. Zhu, Z. Li, C. Zhang, H. Wang, Y. Huang, Y. Chen, H. Haas, J. S. Thompson, E. G. Larsson, M. D. Renzo, W. Tong, P. Zhu, X. Shen, H. V. Poor, and L. Hanzo, "On the road to 6G: Visions, requirements, key technologies, and testbeds," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 25, no. 2, pp. 905–974, 2023.

- [4] C. Pan, H. Ren, K. Wang, J. F. Kolb, M. ElKashlan, M. Chen, M. Di Renzo, Y. Hao, J. Wang, A. L. Swindlehurst, X. You, and L. Hanzo, "Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces for 6G systems: Principles, applications, and research directions," *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 59, no. 6, pp. 14–20, 2021.
- [5] Y. Liu, X. Liu, X. Mu, T. Hou, J. Xu, M. Di Renzo, and N. Al-Dahhir, "Reconfigurable intelligent surfaces: Principles and opportunities," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1546–1577, 2021.
- [6] L. Dai, B. Wang, M. Wang, X. Yang, J. Tan, S. Bi, S. Xu, F. Yang, Z. Chen, M. D. Renzo, C.-B. Chae, and L. Hanzo, "Reconfigurable intelligent surface-based wireless communications: Antenna design, prototyping, and experimental results," *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 45 913–45 923, 2020.
- [7] E. Björnson and L. Sanguinetti, "Power scaling laws and near-field behaviors of massive MIMO and intelligent reflecting surfaces," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 1, pp. 1306–1324, 2020.
- [8] J.-B. Gros, V. Popov, M. A. Odit, V. Lenets, and G. Lerosey, "A reconfigurable intelligent surface at mmWave based on a binary phase tunable metasurface," *IEEE Open Journal of the Communications Society*, vol. 2, pp. 1055–1064, 2021.
- [9] R. Wang, Y. Yang, B. Makki, and A. Shamim, "A wideband reconfigurable intelligent surface for 5G millimeter-wave applications," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 72, no. 3, pp. 2399–2410, 2024.
- [10] A. Araghi, M. Khalily, M. Safaei, A. Bagheri, V. Singh, F. Wang, and R. Tafazolli, "Reconfigurable intelligent surface (RIS) in the sub-6 GHz band: Design, implementation, and real-world demonstration," *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 2646–2655, 2022.
- [11] G. G. Machado, M. A. B. Abbasi, A. McKernan, C. Gu, and D. Zelenchuk, "Wideband dual-polarized 1-bit unit-cell design for mmWave reconfigurable intelligent surface," in *2024 18th European Conference on Antennas and Propagation (EuCAP)*, 2024, pp. 1–4.
- [12] G. Machado, A. McKernan, C. Gu, D. Zelenchuk, M. Saikia, O. Yurduseven, S. Cotton, and M. Abbasi, "A modified 1-bit unit-cell for mmwave ris optimized at extreme incident angle," in *2024 IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and Propagation and INC/USNC-URSI Radio Science Meeting (AP-S/INC-USNC-URSI)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1177–1178.
- [13] H. Yang, F. Yang, S. Xu, Y. Mao, M. Li, X. Cao, and J. Gao, "A 1-bit 10×10 reconfigurable reflectarray antenna: Design, optimization, and experiment," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. 64, no. 6, pp. 2246–2254, 2016.